

ISic0649

Verse inscription recording building of a nymphaeum

Language

Type

Material

Object

Editor

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo Civico di
Catania, inventory 539

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height 53 cm

Width 72 cm

Depth 3 cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Βαιὸν ἐμὲ Νύμφαις ἔργον κάμ [εν]
2. οὐ γάρ μοι σθεναρὴν χεῖρ' ἐπέ [θηκεμάτην]
3. ἀλλ' ἐν ἐμοὶ καμάτων εὔρεν τέλ [ορξῆσχετ'] [ἄγαλμα]
4. ἀγχόθι λαϊνέης αὐλακος ὕδρο [φόρου]
5. τὴν αὐτὸς ποίησεν, ἐς ἡέρα πολλ [ὸνάειρας]
6. νᾶμα φέρειν καθαρὸν ἐνναέται [ςΚατάνης]
7. (vac.undefined) Ἐννοῖου (vac.undefined)

Apparatus

The restorations proposed by Manganaro are adopted here

Translation (en)

[---] wrought me, a humble work for the Nymphs.

Indeed he did not lay his mighty hand upon me in vain,
but in me he found fulfilment of his toils, and gained a statue
next the stony water-bearing furrow
which he himself made, having lifted it high into the air,
to bring a pure stream to those dwelling in Katania.
(verses) of Ennoios.

Translation (it)

[---] mi ha fatto, un umile lavoro per le Ninfe.

Infatti, non mi ha imposto invano la sua potente mano,
ma in me ha trovato compimento dei suoi sforzi e ha ottenuto una
statua

accanto al solco che fornisce l'acqua,
che egli stesso ha fatto, avendolo innalzato fino in cielo,
per portare un flusso puro a coloro che abitano in Catania.
(Versi) di Ennoios.

Commentary

The name of the individual who carried out the work, and is honoured in the text, is lost at the end of line 1. Traces of the aqueduct which brought water into this part of Catania from the south side of Etna survive. Biscari uncovered remains of a complex which it has been suggested is identical with the nymphaeum (fountain house) mentioned in the later Latin text. The fragmentary mosaic of the months preserved in the museum appears to come from the same location. It is possible that this text commemorates the completion/extension of one branch of the aqueduct, and the construction of a nymphaeum at its terminus. Although Latin was the language of public documents, Greek was used occasionally for highly literary texts of this sort, and the two texts provide another illustration of the bilingualism present in Catania at this time.

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